

BENEFITS

- Application to architectural interior walls and furniture or other uses e.g., concrete formwork
- The non-fire-retarded version consists of almost 100% bio-based materials
- Fire-retardancy: the material was classified as V-0 at 4 mm (UL94)
- Customisable exterior finish
- Easy recycling
- Cost efficient

NEXT STEPS

- Upscaling of the production process
- Determination of selected mechanical and physical properties including durability
- Fire classification of final product
- Other applications in construction and furniture, vehicle production, decorative laminates, thermoplastic sheets

Project innovation fact sheet

Thermoplastic composite sheet from recycled wood and biopolymers

APPLICATIONS

- Replacement of High-Pressure Laminate (HPL) as plywood top-sheet
- Applications where HPL acts as top-sheet, and for use on other wood-based panels such as oriented strand board (OSB)